

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

A subset of the data from Cycle 3 simulations has been attributed a DOI and made available to the nextGEMS consortium and the wider scientific community. (Task 3.1)

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WP3

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1 Executive summary

We provide a subset of the Cycle 3 storm-resolving Earth-system simulation output freely available to the nextGEMS consortium and the wider scientific community. The subset includes several frequently used 2D fields, such as atmospheric surface temperature and ocean mixed layer depth. The variables for the IFS-FESOM model are provided on the original 4.5 km resolution grid. For the ICON model, the data is available on a HEALPix grid at zoom level 10, which equates to approximately 6.4 km resolution. This is closely aligned with ICON's original 5 km resolution grid. The dataset is published at [WDCC](#) (World Data Center for Climate)¹, findable via the [doi:10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3](https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3) (Koldunov et al., 2023) and accessible via [WDCC](#).

2 Conclusion & Results

A dataset resulting out of the nextGEMS cycle 3 model development phase is published with an DOI attributed to it.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no

¹<https://www.wdc-climate.de>

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP3	Relevance in this deliverable?
To complete Cycle 3 (Development) simulations (O1).	yes
To finalize the configuration (including associated output and data management requirements) of SR-ESMs for the production simulations (O1).	yes
To perform present day and future projections (i.e., production simulations). (O1/O2)	yes
To organize and curate simulation output for sustainable access beyond the completion of NextGEMS. (O1/O2/O3)	yes
To support the four themes in exploring extensions of SR-ESMs to address additional application needs and testing proposed model improvements. (O1/O2/O3)	yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Within the nextGEMS project the two weather and climate models [ICON](#)² and [IFS](#)³ are developed to simulate 30 years into the future on a storm-resolving scale. The model development is split into three iterative cycles as displayed in Fig 1. In each cycle new features and improvements are implemented and thereupon tested in a simulation spanning at least one annual cycle at 5 km spatial resolution or higher. The simulations are run globally in a coupled configuration. IFS is coupled to the ocean model [FESOM](#)⁴ for the high-resolution runs at 2.8 km and 4 km, while ICON has its own ocean component ICON-O.

Figure 1: The model development in nextGEMS builds upon the work done within the [DYAMOND](#)⁵ initiative and continues in iterative cycles as shown by this graph. The rhombs denote hackathons that evaluate the main simulations towards the end of a development cycle.

4.1 Cycle 3 simulations

This report primarily focuses on the released subset of model data for Cycle 3. To facilitate a better understanding of these datasets, we begin with a concise summary of the most recent adjustments made to the model configurations and the underlying physics in Cycle 3.

4.1.1 ICON

Output:

- The output is now written on the HEALPix grid [Gorski et al. \(2005\)](#). As the grid is new to the community, there is an extensive effort to provide [description and examples](#)⁶ on how to work with HEALPix output on <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/> website.

Ocean:

- New ocean vertical mixing parameter settings.
 - Reduction of c_k parameter from 0.2 to 0.1 (because this improves the equatorial Atlantic zonal SST gradient).
 - Additional Langmuir turbulence parameterisation in TKE scheme switched on (because this very slightly deepens the too shallow mixed layer).
- Activated coupling of sea level pressure (in Cycle 2, this was erroneously not done for the ocean, only for sea ice).

²<https://mpimet.mpg.de/en/science/models/icon-esm/>

³<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/FUG/2+The+ECMWF+Integrated+Forecasting+System++IFS>

⁴<https://fesom.de/>

⁶<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/Processing/healpix/index.html/>

- New spinup with the above changes, otherwise same spinup procedure as in Cycle 2 (e.g. with SST nudging).
- Ocean time step increased.

Atmosphere:

- Fix in sensible heat flux over ocean and sea ice.
- Energy fix in microphysics.
- Horizontal tracer advection set to miura (2nd order, linear reconstruction) with subcycling for all tracers.
- Mixed precision (single precision in parts of the dynamical core).

Land:

- Use land heat capacity/conductivity maps.
- EXTPAR soil texture in hydrology.

An overview of available datasets is provided in the [easy.gems / Cycle 3 simulation](#)⁷ chapter.

4.1.2 IFS**Output:**

- All IFS output has been processed on-the-fly by [multio](#)⁸ and written to a local [FDB](#)⁹.

New IFS cycle 48r1:

A general overview of 48r1 modifications with respect to the previous IFS Cycle 47r3 can be found at <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/FCST/Implementation+of+IFS+Cycle+48r1>. The most important features are:

- A radiatively interactive prognostic ozone using new HLO scheme.
- A new precipitation category: freezing drizzle.
- A revised computation of Semi-Lagrangian advection departure points.
- A new model top sponge layer formulation and semi-Lagrangian vertical filter.

Tuned TOA balance: On top of a significantly reduced global water and energy imbalance that was already available in cycle 2, the TOA radiation imbalance has been tuned by:

- A decrease of a threshold that limits the minimum size of ice effective radius, increasing high clouds in the tropics and therefore reducing outgoing longwave radiation.
- A reduction of cloud edge erosion, increasing low-level cloud amount and therefore reducing TOA net shortwave radiation.

⁷<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/index.html#id3>

⁸<https://github.com/ecmwf/multio>

⁹<https://github.com/ecmwf/fdb>

- A reduction of the cloud inhomogeneity, which increases low-level cloud amount as it reduces the rate of accretion. This change is in line with nextGEMS's km-scale resolutions as cloud inhomogeneity is expected to be smaller at high resolutions.
- A change restricting the detrainment of mid-level convection to the liquid phase in most situations.
- In agreement with nextGEMS Cycle 2 but unlike in the operational IFS, linear rather than cubic interpolation is used for the departure point interpolation of the Semi-Lagrangian advection scheme for all moist species except water vapour.
- A modification of the microphysics for rain and snow evaporation.

Deep convection scheme:

At the highest resolution (4.4 km), instead of switching the deep convection scheme off completely, its activity is strongly reduced (the cloud base mass flux is reduced by a factor of 5 compared to the default value). This results in a realistic PDF of intense precipitation.

Surface-atmosphere interaction upgrades:

- An active urban scheme (McNorton et al., 2023) for the first time in IFS-nextGEMS.
- Modified parameters for snow density (Cao et al., 2022) and soil freezing (Zsoter et al., 2022) for snow-permafrost improvements.
- An improved postprocessing of 2 meter temperature reducing the warm bias present occasionally under very stable conditions (similar to van Meijgaard et al. (2008)).
- A new set of ancillary fields for the surface (climate.v021). The new components in the ancillary fields are:
 - Land Use Land Cover based on ESA-CCI. The new Land Use/Land Cover maps, among other changes, removes or reduces the extension of ambiguous high vegetation types (e.g. interrupted forest, mixed forest, sparse vegetation) and increases the extent of short grass. It also reduces the high vegetation cover and increases the low vegetation cover globally.
 - Leaf Area Index monthly climatology based on Copernicus Global Land Service (GCLS).
 - New Ocean Bathymetry based on GEBCO2021 (GEBCO Compilation Group, 2023).

FESOM ocean model:

- Science changes:
 - Coupling of ocean surface currents
 - More consistent ocean heat flux setting (cooler Southern Ocean)
 - Snow takes heat from the ocean in order to melt when falling into it (cooler Southern Ocean)
 - More consistent heat flux into the ice (shortwave fix)
- Technical changes:

- multi-field coupling, reducing a bottleneck
- Added extra ocean variables (MLD, SST, sea ice conc, ocean currents, 300m-averaged T, S, and depth of 20C isotherm, ..) that are available on IFS grid with its GRIB code.
- Added 3-hourly upper 300m of 3D model levels to better match the Storms & Ocean data request

For a complete overview see [FESOM2.5 release notes](#)¹⁰.

An overview of available datasets is provided in the [easy.gems / Cycle 3 simulation](#)¹¹ chapter.

4.2 Published subset of Cycle 3 model output

The main experiments during Cycle 3 were ngc3028 for ICON (5 years, coupled, 5 km horizontal resolution) and IFS_4.4-FESOM_5-cycle3 for IFS-FESOM (5 years, coupled, atmosphere at ~ 4.4 km, ocean at ~ 5 km).

A subset of the data is published at the [World Data Center for Climate \(WDCC\)](#)¹², a FAIR-enabling discipline-specific long-term archive focusing on the preservation of simulation-based climate science operated at DKRZ. The dataset is published including DOI provision and is further described in the following. Monthly values of selected 2d variables are saved from the main experiments of IFS and ICON.

- surface temperature at 2 m
- wind speed (ICON) and wind components (IFS) at 10 m
- precipitation
- sea surface temperature
- ocean mixed layer depth
- surface sensible and latent heat flux
- net short-wave radiation at top of atmosphere
- outgoing long-wave radiation

Example fields from both models showing some of the above mentioned variables are displayed in Fig. 2. Only the region of Europe is shown to better visualize the rich details of eddies in the ocean or regions of high and low wind speeds in mountainous areas

¹⁰<https://github.com/FESOM/fesom2/releases/tag/2.5>

¹¹<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/index.html#id4>

¹²<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>

Figure 2: Examples showing monthly averages of 2 meter atmospheric temperature (top), near surface wind speed (mid), and the ocean mixed layer depth (bottom) over Europe in January 2020. TODO: WHAT IS ICON, WHAT IS IFS?

4.3 Data access via WDCC

The *Cycle 3* datasets published in the context of this deliverable are findable and accessible via the [WDCC](#) search interface as follows:

Project:

[nextGEMS \(Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems\)](#)¹³

Experiment:

[nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 3 simulations for ICON and IFS](#)¹⁴

Datasets

[ICON model output \(nextGEMS cycle 3\)](#)¹⁵

[IFS-FESOM model output \(nextGEMS cycle 3\)](#)¹⁶

Both datasets are reusable in compliance with CC-BY 4.0 license. The published *Cycle 3* data are globally findable via a DOI assigned at the level of the *experiment*:

DOI:10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3 (Koldunov et al., 2023)

In compliance with the [FAIR](#)¹⁷ principles, all metadata is openly accessible, while the data download is free for registered users. Interested users can register with [WDCC](#). Further, interoperability is achieved through the ensured use of domain-specific (meta)data and file format standards. Reusability is achieved by supplying a standard license (CC-BY 4.0) and rich, domain-specific metadata.

Downloading the data is possible either via the [WDCC](#) graphical web interface or by using the command line tool [jblob](#)¹⁸.

¹³<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/project?acronym=nextGEMS>

¹⁴https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_cyc3

¹⁵https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_cyc3_ICON

¹⁶https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_cyc3_IFS

¹⁷<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/info?site=fairness>

¹⁸<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/info?site=jblob>

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5 Dissemination and uptake

5.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The nextGEMS *Cycle 3* data published and made available to the global scientific community in the framework of this deliverable are of very high general interest, since they represent the first publicly available dataset covering one or two complete annual cycles simulated with state-of-the-art storm-resolving Earth-system models.

Publication of these data in [WDCC](#) facilitates uptake by all stakeholders because

1. [WDCC](#) supplied metadata is indexed in various searchable resources, e.g. Google Dataset Search
2. nextGEMS project reports will reference the data via their unique identifier and provide a citation
3. project-related communication and dissemination activities, e.g. on the project homepage, will include the data citation in the list of project outcomes
4. data reuse is very efficient due to the ensured use of domain-specific (meta)data standards which enable allow low-barrier access and analysis of nextGEMS data

6 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

The delay of this deliverable was communicated with the EC project officer.

7 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

8 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This documentation of the cycle 3 data publication builds a link between the model development teams and the WPs that analyze the model output. In addition, the published data set gives users outside the immediate nextGEMS community to easily access the simulation output data and thus expanding the reach of nextGEMS results.

9 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

10 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>